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THE APPROACH OF A MODERN PEDAGOGUE IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation. Today, the main goal of modernizing the continuous education system and raising the efficiency of education to a new level of quality is aimed at the acquisition of modern knowledge and profession by our youth. It is to ensure that people are aware, sensitive and alert to any danger, harmful influences and currents that exist in this very complicated and dangerous time and take a proper place in the life of our society.

Key words: technology, pedagogical technology, education, teacher, student personality, group work.

ПОДХОД СОВРЕМЕННОГО ПЕДАГОГА К ПОВЫШЕНИЮ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА

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Аннотация. Сегодня основная цель модернизации системы непрерывного образования и поднятия эффективности образования на новый качественный уровень направлена на приобретение нашей молодежью современных знаний и профессии. Целью является обеспечение того, чтобы люди были осведомлены, чувствительны и внимательны к любой опасности, пагубным влияниям и течениям, которые существуют в это очень сложное и опасное время, и заняли подобающее место в жизни нашего общества.

Ключевые слова: технология, педагогическая технология, образование, учитель, личность ученика, групповая работа.

Introduction. It is known that in the social policy of our country, we create harmony between the individual and society by realizing the national identity, mastering national and universal values bringing, the satisfaction of the growth of needs from particular to general in every way requires the research and development of the abilities, talents, internal capabilities, unique individual psychological characteristics of young adults. Formation of the young generation as a person and subject, mental development, without determining the level of education it is impossible to increase the efficiency of secondary special and higher education process [1]. In order to fulfill these noble tasks, the Law "On Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training" were adopted in the 9th session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic on August 29, 1997.

The role of a pedagogue is very important in making young people, who are the foundation of our future, intelligent and intelligent. Therefore, whether the teacher is a technician or a chemist, he should master pedagogical, methodology, and didactics well.

Based on the social needs of society, the current level of science and production, didactics develops its subject of study, such as; the purpose of education (why it is taught, what to prepare the young generation for), the content of education (what is taught), the forms and methods of organization of education (how to teach), as well as accounting and control of its results[2]. Categories of didactics; education, educational process, teaching principles.

Education - includes imparting knowledge and education. Education is, first of all, general and special knowledge, skills, abilities, which are selected for mastering, aimed at personal development, and aimed at preparing for the successful performance of specific activities. secondly, it refers to the results of mastering the content. The category of education includes such concepts as the content of education, curriculum, educational subject, curriculum. We learn these concepts in the process of studying science.

The educational process represents the imparting of knowledge, skills, skills by the teacher as a whole organized process and their assimilation by the students, the formation of various abilities. This process is seen in the activity of the Pedagogue (teaching) and the interaction of students (studying). During the study of this program, we will learn teaching methods, forms of teaching organization, innovations and technologies related to the category of educational process.

The principles of education include important basic rules, based on which it is possible to ensure the effectiveness of education (the practicality of education and the educational process). Teaching principles are divided into two large groups; determining the type and content of training; principles determining the effective organization and existence of the educational process [3].

Today, education aims to develop the intellectual and scientific power of the republic, to form a well-rounded person who understands his responsibility to society and family. As a result of the reforms, special attention is paid to the issue of training pedagogues who can teach in vocational colleges, which are considered a new type of secondary special educational institution.

Today's pedagogue is the main participant in the changes taking place in our life, he must be a mature, deep-knowledge specialist, a person with pedagogical skills and abilities, who knows his social role well.

Teaching is one of the oldest activities. As a result of the social division of labor, it was separated as a separate profession. People are specially trained for the teaching profession. In people who have undergone special training, the activity of learning is highly developed, it is in constant development and movement. A teacher can live by teaching and continuously learning.

Reading is valid in a certain place and time. From this point of view, it has a number of procedural features: implementation based on stages, direct or indirect perception of the things being studied; recalling previously learned knowledge; applying knowledge to familiar and unfamiliar learning situations;

- thinking about the studied phenomena, distinguishing their general and specific symptoms.

"**Reading**" has its own purpose, means, and result. In this sense, it is an activity. But "reading" is not the activity of a single student, on the contrary, "reading" is the activity of young people engaged in the work of learning and mastering.

- **Teaching and learning come** together on the basis of certain normative requirements and create a third activity - education. Teacher's activity leads to students' activity, consistency in teacher's activity ensures consistency in children's activities. Variety in teacher's activity, variety of tools, use of different methods of education cause children's activities to be effective [4]. Normative requirements to be followed in the course of teaching and learning activities are called educational rules.

Results and discussion. We define the concept of technology;

- Technology is a set of methods and ways used in a work, skill, art.

-Technology is the art of processing, changing the state, skills, abilities, and a set of methods of teaching and learning, taking into account the technical resources of people and their interaction.

Cooperative learning. Interactivity ("inter" - "mutual", "act" - "activity") is important in cooperative pedagogy. Interactivity - interaction between the teacher and the student. In the process of transitioning to the development stage of cooperative activity, there is an increase in the level of self-evaluation from the evaluation of the action of interaction. This process is one of the most important factors indicating the dynamics of cooperation. Game technologies, which are examples of cooperation based on "Subject-Subject" relations, form children's creative abilities, develop independent thinking, broad observation skills. Educational activity of students in small groups can be organized in the form of a game (quiz, brain ring, tournament, competition) and individually [5]. Below are examples of such technologies. In pedagogical technology, the role of the student in the educational process and the attitude of the pedagogue towards the students are important. The following technologies can be distinguished:

a) Authoritarian technology. In this, the pedagogue is the main subject of the educational process, and the student participates only as an object. It is based on the stifling of students' freedom, forced teaching, stifling of initiative, and heavy-handed conduct of the educational process.

b) Didactocentric technologies - they are distinguished by not paying attention to the personality of the student. In this, too, there is a subject-object relationship, and it consists of didactic tools to form a person.

v) Person- oriented technologies - at the center of this is the creation of all conditions for the development of the student's personality, helping to manifest his educational potential. In this case, the student person is not only a subject, but a subject with priority. In this, it becomes the goal of the educational system. Such technologies are called "anthropocentric technologies". Thus, person-oriented technologies are anthropocentric, humanistic and psychotherapeutic, all-round free, creatively developed personality education.

g) Humanistic - personal technologies - distinguished by humanistic essence, helps and supports it. Respect for the power of the student, helping him to discover his abilities and compulsory education rejects education.

d) Collaborative technologies - it promotes the ideas of democracy, equality, and is based on subject-subject in teacher-student relationship. The

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teacher and the student develop the content of educational goals. He evaluates his activities with cooperation.

e) Free education technology - it gives the student the right to choose freely in all directions. During the choice, the student represents the subject from the point of view and follows the result not by external influence, but by means of internal power.

j) Esoteric technology - these are based on esoteric ("unrealized, knowing") knowledge - the truth and the paths leading to it. In this case, the pedagogical process does not consist of informing and communicating, but rather of connecting to the truth. In the exotic paradigm, man himself becomes the center of mutual information exchange with the universe [6].

According to the categories of students, pedagogical technologies are divided into:

- Family (traditional) technology – it is based on the average student.
- Level of information technology (in-depth teaching of subjects) - gymnasium, lyceum, special education.
- Different kinds of bititimalogic - (surda pedagogy, heat, oligophreno pedagogy).
- Technologies designed to work with difficult and gifted students.

Technologies built on the basis of modernization and modification of existing training systems:

A) Pedagogical technologies based on humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations. Sh. A. Amomashvili's cooperative, humane - personal technology is included.

B) Pedagogical technologies built on the basis of activation and intensification of students' activities. For example, game technologies, educational technologies based on Shatalov's "base s - konspector #1".

V) Pedagogical technologies based on the effectiveness of organization and management of the teaching process. Pedagogical technologies based on the organization and management of the effectiveness of the teaching process, for example, Programmatic teaching, differentiated teaching technology, Individualized Teaching technology. Group and team methods of teaching, Computer technologies

D) Alternative technologies: Steiner's "Waldrovo pedagogy", Freyne's "Free labor technology", Probable educational technology. Technologies designed to build the educational process on the basis of problems Relevance of team teaching The importance of these pedagogical technologies is that it allows to open the

accumulated problems and contradictions of modern education. All pedagogues recognize the crisis in traditional education. It is evident in the following conflicts:

1. The conflict between motivation and motivation to teach students. Educators complain that students are not learning, and students complain that learning is boring, monotonous, and lacking in power. Team teaching is formed and developed based on the cooperation of the motivation of the pedagogues.

2. The teacher explains the new topic, the others listen. This can continue throughout the lesson. And team teaching encourages each student to work actively during the lesson.

3. Conflict between psychological comfort and discomfort. In a typical classical lesson, the teacher should hold the whole class in his hands for 1 hour and 20 minutes. The team teaching method creates conditions for non-forced and interesting communication.

4. Conflict between education and training. In a normal lesson, the mutual educational influence of students is limited by the words "don't talk" and "don't teach" by the teacher. In group teaching, on the contrary, the words "Discuss", "Correct", "Evaluate each other" are used.

5. Conflict between individual development and teaching standards: On September 1st, 30 students came to the classroom, and by June 1st, all of them should move from class to class. Rivin called it herd crossing. In group teaching, the student can come to the class at any time and take the exam at any time.

Methodology of group teaching methods Group teaching methods require compliance with the following principles:

1. Having a changing pair of students;
2. Their teaching each other;
3. Mutual control;
4. Mutual management.

Sh.A.Amonshvili's humanitarian-personal technology. "Dedicate yourself to children" Academician Shalva Aleksandrovich Amonashvili developed and implemented cooperative pedagogy in his experienced school. The result of pedagogical activity is the technology "School Life". The purpose of Sh. Amonashvili's technology is as follows: - to create an opportunity to develop the characteristics of a perfect person in a child by solving personal qualities. - placing kindness and goodness in the child's mind and heart. - To provide conditions for deep and thorough assimilation of knowledge and studies.

Conclusion. In each of these directions, education is organized taking into account the interest, ability, opportunity and conditions of the student. Especially in the person-oriented education, a special emphasis is placed on the formation of the student's ability to try to get out of problematic situations through independent thinking. It is important to understand the importance of independent learning, trying to solve problems without the help of the teacher in difficult situations in the educational process, and only then relying on the help of the teacher to make sure that his conclusions are correct.

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